

1 Planning a digitally integrated future: 2 GIS and BIM for roman architecture, 3 the case of Pompeii Archaeological 4 Park

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18 The ongoing wave of digitization across scientific domains is reshaping the fields of cultural
19 heritage and archaeology. Nevertheless, as demonstrated by previous research, the
20 exceptional nature of heritage historic assets often conflicts with software architectures, such
21 as data schemas and communication protocols, that are not conceived with those specific
22 requirements in mind. The archaeological remains preserved within the Pompeii Archaeological
23 Park constitute an extraordinary case study, where architectural features have been preserved
24 almost in their entirety. Given this configuration, any digital management tool designed to
25 support the site's conservation must integrate the functionalities of both Building Information
26 Modelling (BIM) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), ensuring their seamless
27 interoperability.

28 This study offers a quantitative evaluation of this interoperability challenge-frequently mentioned
29 in articles but not demonstrated yet-by identifying the precise information loss that occurs during
30 the digitization process and the following alignment with established data standards.

31 Specifically, a semantic mapping between the entities involved in the process is presented: the
32 open-format standards IFC (for BIM) and CityGML (for GIS) are compared with a purpose-built
33 taxonomy developed for Vesuvian Roman architecture.

34 The resulting correspondence matrix indicates the conceptual relationships across schemas,
35 assessing their instrumental relevance for archaeologists, conservators, and site managers.

36 To further enrich the semantic representation of archaeological data, the research explored the
37 possibilities given by ontologies and thesauri. This approach allowed for the definition of
38 domain-specific concepts and relationships that are not adequately captured by existing BIM
39 and GIS standards, thereby aligning the data more closely with archaeological practices.

40 All this constitutes a foundational step toward the development of an integrated digital system
41 that bridges the BIM, GIS and ontological domains, while remaining responsive to the
42 methodological principles and operational needs articulated by archaeological experts.

43 **Keywords:** BIG_SMAART, BIM, GIS, semantics, Pompeian architecture

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Introduction

45 This contribution is part of the broader context of the digital framework for the digitisation of
46 archaeological assets. Nowadays, there are many studies that highlight the exceptional nature
47 of historical heritage and how it clashes with software, schemas, or data protocols that have not
48 been specifically constructed with archaeology's needs in mind (Bosco et al., 2021; Bosco et
49 al., 2019; Garagnani et al., 2020).

50 During the last decades -as well as in the past- archaeology has looked tirelessly for creative
51 and satisfying solutions to represent both the complex status quo and the development of
52 archaeological sites. Its complicated long relationship with digital representation tools is part of
53 this on-going research, one that started several years ago, mainly with GIS (Geographic
54 Information Systems) representation. Then, with the popularity of BIM increasing in the sector,
55 the demand for its integrations to GIS drastically grew, and the first experiments in this regard
56 started almost simultaneously (Delpozzo & Balletti, 2023)

57 Within this context, the aim of this investigation is to define a theoretical structure necessary
58 for the organisation of the heterogeneous data that contribute to the study of archaeological
59 evidence, identifying in the relevant available schemas the points of connection between
60 representation systems such as BIM, GIS and the archaeological domain.

61 The BIG_SMAART project, funded by the Italian Ministry of Universities and Research,
62 involves the co-operation of three universities: the University of Naples L'Orientale, the
63 University Federico II of Naples and the Politecnico di Milano.

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Figure 1 - Project workflow with division of the various phases

66 The aim of this project is to provide a quantitative assessment of the interoperability between
67 these systems. Although the topic is widely known in the literature, it is still rare to find research
68 demonstrating what information is lost during digitisation processes and the compliance
69 between the most widely used data schemas in BIM and GIS.

70 Considering these assumptions, to define the specific workflow (Fig. 1), it was decided to
71 define three main research questions:

72 (a) do current GIS and BIM data schemas or existing ontologies dedicated to archaeology
73 meet the requirements for the representation of ancient architecture and especially Vesuvian
74 architecture?

75 (b) does a data schema support these requirements better than its equivalent?

76 (c) how can BIM and GIS methods be integrated in an archaeological context?

77 The research aims to address these questions through the analysis of a concrete case study
78 in which data formats have been applied and evaluated.

79 To this purpose, the project's methodology is based on the analysis of how the semantic
80 data provided by these systems overlap with the archaeological needs. Since the
81 archaeological world is so wide-ranging, the experimentation focuses on the Vesuvian area,
82 which is unique because it was crystallised in 79 AD. Thanks to this condition, the context
83 reveals extensive information about life and technology in the Roman world of the Republican
84 and early Imperial periods.

85 More specifically, we propose a semantic mapping between the entities that are part of the
86 process, starting from an analysis of the most widely used open format standards for BIM and
87 GIS, namely IFC and CityGML. We then proceeded to compare the semantic possibilities
88 offered by these formats with the semantic tree created specifically for Roman architecture in
89 the Vesuvius area.

90 **Digital Data Management in the Pompeian context**

91 The archaeological analysis of evidence and construction techniques was extended to allow
92 the creation of a semantic tree (a schematic hierarchical model) useful for breaking down the
93 single elements of the complex archaeological reality of Pompeii. The choice of the site is linked
94 to various reasons, which can be summarised in the following points:

- 95 • Extensive, well-preserved archaeological evidence, on which to test as many
96 cases as possible;
- 97 • Evidence for which there is a good level of previous documentation, even when
98 it concerns excavations carried out in past centuries;
- 99 • A complex reality to manage, characterised by modern infrastructure that adapts
100 to ancient evidence;
- 101 • The volume of evidence requires an informatic system capable of providing
102 effective management support.

103 Over time, the Park has implemented, through the Great Pompeii Project, research actions
104 focused on the collection and systematisation of data with a precise view to preventive
105 maintenance. In particular, the so-called "Knowledge Plan"¹ has led to the creation of SiPompei,
106 a georeferenced and relational platform that describes and catalogues the entire ancient city,
107 joined by Open Pompeii (<https://open.pompeiiisites.org/index.html>), a digital archive with free
108 access aimed at facilitating the dissemination of data that is integrated with SIAV (information
109 system of the Vesuvian area) and Tolomeo for archival materials and historical documentation.

¹ The data from the GPP_Knowledge Plan has been kindly provided by the Archaeological Park of Pompeii.

110 The Knowledge Plan has also produced new 3D survey documentation with laser-scanning
111 and photogrammetric methodologies covering the entire surface of the Park as of 2015. This
112 three-dimensional documentation, however, is unrelated to the systems mentioned above.

113 It therefore follows that the conservation and management requirements for such a complex
114 site would necessitate the combined use of BIM and GIS functionalities.

115 Based on these assumptions, the initial phase of the research involved an in-depth review
116 of the state of the art regarding the integration of BIM and GIS applied to archaeology. The
117 analysis of the literature made it possible to identify the data formats most frequently attested
118 in previous studies, the software most adopted in this field of investigation, as well as to define
119 the main problems met by other research groups with the aim of setting up an efficient mapping
120 between the entities belonging to these knowledge structures we are aiming to communicate.

121 **The choice of the case study**

122 To verify the theoretical model defined at the outset of the project, an application case was
123 identified and selected.

124 The choice of the House - Bakery VIII, 6, 1-9/11 (Fig. 2), is linked to several factors: the
125 location of the complex between two public areas, the Civil forum and the Triangular forum; a
126 complex stratigraphic sequence with various modifications and restorations, including modern
127 ones; the type of building structure that was transformed from a private house into a productive
128 activity with the addition of peculiar installations such as the oven and millstones.

129 The archaeological complex was already discovered at the end of the 19th century, but it is
130 still almost unstudied². Therefore, a census and cataloguing of the architectural and functional
131 elements of the complex, as well as the building techniques and materials used for their
132 construction, was carried out (Borriello et al., 2025).

133 Although not widely known to the general public, the Domus — in addition to occupying a
134 strategic position within the topographical framework of the ancient city — is perfectly suited to
135 the experimental needs of the project due to its structural complexity and its multi-layered
136 chronological and functional stratification.

² The first excavations took place between 1881 and 1882.

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Figure 2 - Photo of the oven installed in place of the cubiculum east in the atrium of the House - Bakery VIII, 6, 1-9/11 (Courtesy of the Archaeological Park of Pompeii)

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The semantic breakdown of Vesuvian constructions

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To make the management of the evidence as suitable as possible for its use with BIM and GIS platforms, a semantic breakdown of private construction elements in Pompeii was carried out (Fig. 3). The semantic scheme was based on the HBIM model, where entities are described as: Class, Category, Type and Instance, attempting to adapt it within the limits of archaeological requirements. The main components of the Roman building were divided into three disciplines (structural, architectural and plant engineering), based on the function of the object in the Roman building complex. Each discipline was then divided into classes or sets, i.e. elements that share the same formal and functional characteristics (wall, coin, pillar), which can be divided into subclasses or subsets, based on the variation of certain characteristics (e.g. rectangular pillar, square pillar, oval pillar). This is followed by categories, which allow the class to be broken down into constituent elements (e.g. column, which is subdivided into capital, shaft and base). Likewise, the subcategory allows the order or building technique used to be defined (e.g. *opus incertum* shaft). Finally, the type indicates the material used (e.g. limestone); the instance, on the other hand, constitutes the individual object created (Borriello et al., 2025).

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157 **Figure 3** - Semantic structure of Pompeian architecture (developed by G. Borriello based on
158 the data in attached n.1)

159 In addition to being assigned an ID during modelling, each instance was accompanied by a
160 set of data that allows for the management of archaeological information in various ways. The
161 modelling phase and subsequent implementation of BIM objects were structured to combine,
162 on the one hand, a broad pattern of archaeological requirements and, on the other hand, to
163 avoid overloading the BIM system. All this required operational choices to be made (Carpentiero
164 - D'Auria 2023): the addition of numerous families available locally would make it possible to
165 compensate for the lack of archaeological elements within the BIM platform; however, this could
166 lead to the possible loss of essential data during export.

167 Among other necessary choices, it was useful to refer to the data management system of
168 the Archaeological Park of Pompeii for the nomenclature of the walls. This system involves
169 dividing a single wall into two different sides, so in the information set for each instance, it was
170 necessary to add a field that would allow the two separate sides to be joined into a single wall
171 entity.

172 Another choice involved the introduction of a code to identify elements other than walls, such
173 as floors, ceilings and cladding.

174 Lastly, necessary choices concerned the reconstruction of the quoins, identified as sections
175 of masonry, and the doorways, which were modelled as empty spaces. These examples are
176 just a few of the difficulties that are evident in the modelling phase. For this reason, it was clear
177 that there was a need to compare the semantics of Roman architecture with IFC formats and
178 the main ontologies of the archaeological domain.

179 **The semantic comparison between data schemas**

180 IFC³ is both the schema and exchange format more widely used in the BIM domain. The
181 hierarchical structure that arranges classes in descending order and connects them through
182 specific relationships is actually very complex and at the same time descriptive: at the point of
183 development it reached nowadays (with the version 4x3 of the standard) it can be argued that

³ BuildingSMART Alliance 2024, Industry Foundation Classes Release 4.3 ADD2 (IFC 4.3 ADD2) (<https://standards.buildingsmart.org/>).

184 IFC, of the available and approved-on data schema is the more advanced in the semantic
185 description of built assets; it was put to the comparison with the created “pompeian” classes
186 and a mapping (connection) was performed to the more semantically correspondent. The
187 correspondence was registered both in a spreadsheet and graphically.

188 As an example, in Fig. 4, we position the class ifcWall, its declination in “Opera Vittata” and
189 the materials that make it up and determine the type. The various wall “instances” (entities in
190 the project) will inherit these characteristics.

191 In a comparison work of complete mapping of entities, a missing percentage relationship
192 was estimated for several elements such as quoin, arch or threshold, for which there are no IFC
193 classes.

194 Going into the specifics of the class “Wall”, the declination in the typology standard was also
195 analysed. As can be seen graphically from the mapping connections in Fig. 5, the “Archaeo-
196 Wall” class (on the left) corresponds to the ifcWall class of the 4x3 standard (on the right), the
197 latest official version. The typologies, on the other hand, flow into an ifcWallType unique class
198 where the various specifications due to building works and materials can subsequently be
199 created inside the project. Optionally, the various instances can take on an additional
200 Enumerative Type which, however, does not help to better specify the semantics at the level
201 required by the archaeological needs.

202 The same mapping process was carried out with CityGML , the de-facto semantic standard
203 in the geospatial sciences. Designed for representations at the urban scale, which includes
204 morphological data for built and natural environments, similarly to IFC has a dually structured
205 nature (with geometry and information combined) but it is operates in the Geography Markup
206 Language (GML).

207 Due to the number of classes (named “features”) available, CityGML is subdivided in
208 interconnected modules, that connect through the same hierarchy. This standard is flatter and
209 less descriptive than IFC, and customisation mechanisms have to be employed that deviate
210 from the predefined classes to reach good. The definition of types is less complete than the IFC
211 because it must be reproduced with a customised mechanism called “CodeList”. Using the
212 example illustrated before, specifically for the class “WALL”, this flows into the “Building
213 Constructive Element”, a very generic concept, while the types of flow into the “CodeList”, which
214 is not globally approved (Rosignoli et al., 2025).

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Figure 5 - in the image, an extract from the visual mapping performed between the classes of the ex-novo hierarchical “tree” constructed for the archaeological entities and the partial hierarchical schema of IFC 4X3. The extract focuses on wall entities. It is clear from the number of arrows that often converge in the same direction towards IFC classes that there is a loss of semantic granularity. The complete archaeological classes “tree” on the left and a zoom-in on the entity wall in “opera incerta” (developed by O. Rosignoli in *Miro*, based on the data in attached n.2)

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The possibilities provided by ontologies: an overview

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The need to align this semantic decomposition with the most popular standard formats required the integration of data with additional systems capable of supporting this type of description. This led to a reflection on conceptual representation tools and semantic interoperability closer to the archaeological domain, directing an analysis of what is already available in the current landscape and what alternatives they presented for the description of the entities of the archaeological semantic tree. Evidence of this can be found in ontologies, i.e. conceptual models that provide a formal structure to describe information in a systematic and interoperable way. The system of ontologies has found wide application in cultural heritage as it provides a common language for the description of the asset, allows a standardization of terms and concepts to ensure a uniform description, favours interoperability between systems and supports more advanced and precise research, since it enables data to be queried based on concepts and their relationships, not only on textual terms. In addition, these systems allow for providing adequate support in the identification of classes and properties to be included in the semantic tree of the archaeological building, where the conceptual structure offered by the BIM and GIS systems does not sufficiently meet the needs of archaeological documentation.

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In particular, the research involved the analysis of international and national ontologies and thesauri:

245 • On the international scene, the best-known and most widely used domain ontology is
246 the CIDOC-CRM⁴, an ISO standard that provides the basic classes and relationships designed
247 for the world of cultural heritage. It has a "core" version and a series of modular extensions,
248 designed to support different types of specialized research and documentation queries, which
249 can be integrated to further enrich the descriptions; of particular interest for the aims of this
250 research is the CRMba (Buildings Archaeology) extension⁵, whose semantic model allows to
251 identify the structure of which an archaeological building is composed and the relationships
252 between the parts, supporting the process of recording evidence and material discontinuities
253 on archaeological buildings. Very interesting is the possibility of defining empty spaces created
254 with intention (e.g., a door or a window), giving us the possibility to distinguish it from a structural
255 collapse (Ronzino, 2016). Another extension of particular importance for this project is
256 represented by CRMarchaeo⁶, a semantic model developed to support the archaeological
257 excavation process and the activities related to it. The richness of the stratigraphic relationships
258 provided by CRMarchaeo has proven to be particularly effective in capturing and representing
259 the complex network of connections between the various elements of the archaeological
260 semantic tree. Furthermore, the possibility of harmonizing the CRMba and CRMarcheo
261 extensions enables the integration of complementary perspectives and terminologies, thereby
262 enhancing the overall semantic depth and expressiveness of the resulting model (Ronzino,
263 2017).

264 • ArCo⁷, on the other hand, is the Knowledge Graph of the Italian Cultural Heritage,
265 developed to provide a comprehensive and interoperable semantic infrastructure for the
266 representation, integration, and dissemination of cultural heritage data. The system is structured
267 as a network of thirteen interrelated ontologies, each addressing specific conceptual aspects of
268 the cultural heritage domain and data from the General Catalogue of the Italian Ministry of
269 Cultural Heritage and Activities (MiBAC), published as RDF. This articulated network builds
270 upon and extends well-established conceptual frameworks, indirectly reusing and aligning
271 classes and properties that have been validated in other reference ontologies such as DOLCE,
272 CIDOC CRM, Europeana Data Model (EDM), and BIBFRAME, among others. Such reuse
273 ensures semantic coherence and interoperability within the wider ecosystem of cultural heritage
274 knowledge representation.

275 Among the various ArCo modules, several are of particular interest for the project: in addition
276 to the *core* ontology, two extensions stand out for their relevance to the description of built
277 heritage, that is the 'Construction Description' ontology which introduces a specific semantic
278 framework for representing the structural and material aspects of architectural artefacts,
279 including information about construction techniques, building components, and phases of
280 development; complementarily the 'Denotative Description' ontology provides mechanisms for
281 the refinement and contextualization of descriptive attributes, enabling a more detailed and
282 expressive representation of cultural entities. Taken together, these modules significantly
283 enhance the semantic richness and expressive capacity of ArCo, making it a robust and
284 versatile framework for representing archaeological building heritage within a Linked Open Data
285 environment.

286 The need to rely on multiple ontologies arose from the fact that each of them provides
287 specific classes and properties suited to address the different features identified within the
288 archaeological semantic tree.
289 Nevertheless, in many cases, particularly concerning the highly specific subcategories, a fully
290 satisfactory correspondence could not be found among the examined ontologies. This limitation

⁴ <https://cidoc-crm.org/> the core module and the extensions were last accessed on May 2025

⁵ <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmba>

⁶ <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmarchaeo>

⁷ <http://wit.istc.cnr.it/arco>, last accessed May 2025

291 highlighted the inherent difficulty of representing the full complexity and heterogeneity of the
292 archaeological record within a single conceptual framework.

293 To achieve a more appropriate level of semantic granularity, the research was therefore
294 extended to include the use of thesauri, which are controlled vocabularies that enable a
295 coherent and standardized organization of information related to cultural resources. By
296 integrating thesauri, it becomes possible to refine and enrich the descriptive capacity of the
297 model, providing additional terms and hierarchical relations that can complement the formal
298 logic of the ontologies.

299 Moreover, the use of thesauri facilitates semantic alignment and interoperability across
300 different systems and datasets. Through their publication in SKOS⁸ (Simple Knowledge
301 Organization System), thesauri can be seamlessly incorporated into ontological environments,
302 allowing for the linking of concepts, the reconciliation of terminological variations, and the
303 enhancement of data discoverability. In this way, the combined use of ontologies and thesauri
304 contributes to building a more flexible, expressive, and interoperable semantic ecosystem for
305 the representation of archaeological knowledge.

306 The thesaurus that best meets our needs was the AAT, i.e. *the Art and Architecture*
307 *Thesaurus*, developed by the Getty Research Institute⁹. It is the thesaurus that offers the
308 greatest specificity for description, following a controlled structure of elements from ancient
309 architecture. In the AAT thesaurus, it was possible to find a very detailed semantics of specific
310 elements such as threshold, sacrarium, aedicule, and impluvium.

311 In some cases, the correspondence was as detailed as that provided by IFC format; an
312 example could be the case of the class “wall”: for instance, in ArCo’s hierarchy, the most
313 detailed class is similarly represented by “wall”. Instead, in the CIDOC ontological network, the
314 description of architectural building elements stops at the class B3 ‘Filled Morphological Building
315 Section’ provided by CRMba extension. To further specify the concept, the CRMba has to be
316 connected to the thesaurus entry through a property. In this way, the concept taken from the
317 thesaurus can be treated as a valid class for comparison mapping. Similarly, the thesaurus
318 provides terms to define materials, which can likewise be used as classes within the model.

319 Thesauri, by offering a wide range of lexical entries, have proven essential in instances
320 where the correspondence with the IFC format was inadequate and where existing domain
321 ontologies lacked the granularity required for full semantic alignment with archaeological needs
322 (Fig.6). This issue emerged, for example, in relation to architectural elements such as *cantonalì*
323 (quoins) and specific material like the yellow tuff, where precise correspondence was found in
324 the AAT Thesaurus.

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>

⁹ <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/>

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326 Fig.6: the configuration of the mapping between the archaeo-classes and the CIDOC-CRM
 327 ontology combined with Getty AAT; in the example, wall masonry technologies¹⁰.

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Conclusions

330 Starting from the semantic decomposition of the Vesuvian architecture, all elements were
 331 compared with the most used formats in the field of HBIM, GIS and Ontologies. Findings from
 332 the case study demonstrate that current specialized formats remain insufficient to fully represent
 333 the material and structural complexity of archaeological sites, indicating the necessity for further
 334 optimization or the creation of new interoperable standards.

335 The Big_SMAART project therefore defined the differences in the representation of
 336 architectural entities and materials, which are fundamental for archaeologists for both systems.
 337 A specific semantic mapping for Vesuvian architecture has been developed and it has been
 338 created a correspondence matrix between specific archaeological elements and the solutions
 339 offered by existing digital formats. In this regard, the national and international ontological
 340 models already available for the cultural heritage domain, which guarantee the formalisation of
 341 basic conceptual structures, provided fundamental support.

342 Future work therefore points towards the construction of better performing data schemas
 343 and ontologies for the archaeological domain. Another possible approach to be tested on the
 344 case study would be to construct a custom-made ADE (the "Application Domain Extension",
 345 official extension mechanism of CityGML) to include all the Pompeian classes without
 346 compromises. This would hinder interoperability with other existing CityGML datasets, but at
 347 the same time provide an environment without the many semantics compromises produced by
 348 IFC adaptation or codelist mechanism. Lastly, we remember that this mapping analysis
 349 performed on semantic classes of the standards is not complete without considering a

¹⁰ Developed by O. Rosignoli in *Miro*, with data that are still under examination and development.

350 thoroughly mapping of the relationships between entities and without considering the relation
351 of semantics to the model geometries.

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362 **Conflict of interest disclosure**

363 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of
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